

Optimal Control Strategy to Analyse the Networked Control System Stability

Brijraj Singh Solanki

Professor, Department of Computer Engineering, Poornima College of Engineering, Jaipur, India

ABSTRACT: It is crucial to preserve the networked control systems (NCS) transient performance and stability because adding uncertain parameters degrades system performance and introduces instability. Thus, the analysis of NCS system performance under uncertain conditions, such as disturbance, is the focus of this paper. The performance of NCS is demonstrated using control action and some appropriate stability conditions.

The simulation diagram in result section displays effectiveness of proposed methodology and shows a comparative analysis of the response signal with and without control action along with disturbance in NCS. Experiments conducted in the MATLAB Simulink environment demonstrate the efficacy of the suggested methodology.

KEYWORDS: Packet loss, delay, proportional integral control (PID), Kalman filter, networked control system, and denial of service (DoS).

1. INTRODUCTION

It has been noted that information transmission through communication networks has become increasingly important due to the rapid advancement of technology. The literature review demonstrates that hackers are cautious when gathering data by breaking into a network. Attackers can create and execute an attack on a NCS to reduce control performance using the information provided. Numerous examples of attacks have been documented in literature, including the Maroochy water attack, the Stuxnet worm, the cyber grid attack, and the cyber-attack on the German Steel Mill [1].

The author proposed a networked-predictive policy to instantly regulate closed-loop performance in response to network cues. Additionally covered were the necessary conditions for stability, which rely on transmitting data loss and latency for the closed-loop NCS [2], [3]. The NCS stabilization problem with random packet losses is examined in paper [3]. Stability analysis shows that the multi-objective system with uncertainty bound to the suggested method more closely approximates the discrete time system. The author talked about the constrained optimal-switching control problem with an industrial NCS by excluding exogenous dynamics that degrade performance. The attack order in the process was represented by a random distribution procedure, which was used to detect malicious behavior of Industrial NCS. Additionally, the Bernoulli distribution process is employed to model delay [4].

It is observed the control performance improvement plan for the disrupted NCS during a DoS attack. To combat denial-of-service attacks, an event-triggered predictive control methodology is also provided. A controller verifying the system states converged to an alternative invariant set is assessed while taking the disturbance model into account. The author also covered the necessary stability conditions to ensure that the closed loop NCS system is uniformly definitively bound [5].

This paper's primary contribution is an analysis of how external uncertainty and disturbances affect networked control systems. The performance of NCS is demonstrated using control action and some appropriate stability conditions.

This paper is partitioned into the following sections: The section 2 contains the extensive literature review that was done in order to identify the issue. The problem formulation and mathematical expression are defined in Section 3. Section 4 shows the results of the simulation. Section 5 provides support for the final conclusion and future work.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In order to mitigate the effects and prevent the obtrusive intended data, stability conditions and optimized control schemes were presented. To alleviate the effects of attacks and intentional disruptions on the NCS, the Kalman-filter, Linear Gaussian Control, and PID controller were introduced. In the face of uncertainties, the design efficiently approximates the system and measurement states. Additionally, the author used optimization algorithms to compute system identification parameters and optimize coefficients, which

were then applied to model the intended attack for creating a compromised system [6]. Additionally, certain control laws conditions were presented in [7], [8], [9] to enhance the closed loop networked system's performance.

The co-design framework for stabilization control that was presented for NCS under DoS attack. It also reveals that the controller updates the data using an event-based triggering approach and that the state is measured on a periodic basis. For a given sampling rate and dynamic event triggering, the gain was calculated. Control updates have reportedly decreased and performance against DoS has improved [10]. In order to lessen the impact of malicious attacks and network imperfections, a predictive control for networked-connected control systems (NCCS) was introduced. It is stated that the adopted methodology enhanced system stability and transient performance for varying packet loss values [11], [12].

Using the Bernoulli distribution white sequence, several network imperfections, like packet loss and delay, were modeled. The effects of these parameters on NCS were then examined. To demonstrate the efficacy of the approach, some appropriate stability conditions involving linear matrix inequalities and Lyapunov stability were stated [13], [14], [15].

Additionally, for industrial networked control systems (iNCS), the benefits of optimal control design were explored in [16] along with uncertainty parameters like packet loss and network delay. This design demonstrated the enhanced iNCS transient performance. The effectiveness was assessed with varying packet loss rates and network delays. The author of this paper concentrated on the mean square stabilization issue that occurs in NCS as a result of the long and fading channel. Moreover, the author used the algebraic Riccati equation to present the stability condition [17], [18].

In [19], [20] the impact of instabilities terms on NCS is examined, and it is shown that attacks can be announced via a communication channel in either a forward or backward direction. The impact of process and measurement noise, in addition to these deliberate attacks, on the networked control system's system performance is examined using the Kalman Filter (KF) and adequate stability conditions. The continuous-time NCS using induced delay and packet loss is assessed using the event-triggered scheme designed for channel sharing. Event-triggered and Lyapunov functions are used to analyze the performance parameter and controller, illustrating the efficacy of the approach that has been presented [21], [22]. Additionally, the impact of packet loss in networked systems has been assessed in [23], [24], [25].

The Bernoulli distribution process was used to analyze the NCS time delay and packet loss issue. When state feedback control design is included, network control systems perform better, as shown by the exponential stability condition [26], [27].

In this article, the network effects of random delay and packet loss for the nonlinear stabilization NCS problem were covered. To simulate a fuzzy switched system with an unknown dynamic parameter, the T-S fuzzy model was introduced. Using slow and fast switching dwell time methodology, the exponential stability was presented [28]. Additionally, an observer-based stability problem involving packet loss and time delay in both directions—sensor-controller and vice versa—was examined for NCS. Additionally, the author calculates the stabilized closed loop system's gain matrix.

A backward difference equation is used to analyze the discrete-time proportional derivative controller in the presence of packet loss and random network-delay. The effectiveness of the planned controlled NCS experienced packet loss in the True-Time simulator. The results demonstrated that when a packet is lost, the battery uses more energy [29], [30]. A neural network-based technique for identifying anomalies in a communication channel was presented by the author. Due to time delays and packet loss, NCS experienced uncertainty. Additionally, in [31] the authors provided a comparative analysis approach that compared the performance of the reference trajectory when the system parameters were changing using a neural network-based controller and a conventional proportional integral controller.

A controller was created using a back-stepping technique for a nonlinear networked system. In order to tackle this issue, a number of fuzzy logic techniques are proposed, and a nonlinear function prediction is made. According to the above-mentioned strategy, one can distinguish the input delay by employing an auxiliary signal. Using a switching controller solves the stability issue caused by packet loss and delay. The cone-complementarity-linearization (CCL) algorithm was also used to present sufficient conditions of stability [32]. The topic of designing H-infinity controllers for event-triggered NCS in the face of quantization and denial-of-service attacks is further covered in this article. Next, the necessary and sufficient conditions to ensure the exponential stability of the NCS system in the presence of quantization and denial were derived using the time-varying Lyapunov functional method [33].

A novel technique for identifying abnormalities brought on by attacks that are specifically impacted by packet losses and network delays was presented in paper [34]. This method is intended to detect cyber-attacks that target communication networks. The detection residual was used by the proposed observer-centered strategy to identify network attacks. The observer gain matrix design is aided

by the application of LMI-based techniques. The upper bound for network delay is also determined, and the asymptotic stability of the networked system is discussed using an event-triggering methodology [35]. In paper [36], the delta operator was used to solve robust fault detection problems in NCS with packet dropout and time-varying delay. The Markovian jump system is used, and the transformation of the time delay results in parameter uncertainties in the system model.

This paper presents a co-design approach state feedback control gains and event triggered condition for NCSs with packet loss and short network-induced delays. Because the design is based on a switched model, exponential stability of the system is guaranteed. Furthermore, a self-triggered condition emerges. Ultimately, a numerical example demonstrates that the suggested approach lowers the control signal update frequency to a predetermined point in order to preserve system performance [37].

The problem of fault detection in wireless NCS experiencing packet loss was examined in the paper [38]. The author also takes into account a model class that has multiple disruptions and time delays. It is also assumed that packet loss happens between the actuator and controller. The author provided a sufficient condition using a Lyapunov approach, and the fault observer is represented as a switching discrete time linear system with time-delay [39].

The author calculated the upper bound on packet loss and induced delay while taking the NCS decay rate into account, which limited the control system's maximum overshoot. Using Lyapunov-Krasovskii techniques, a set of stability conditions was also derived [40]. The transmission technique known as event triggering was used to solve the distributed NCS's packet loss and delay issues. For the subsystem to be stable for the input signal, the author designed a controller. In order to make the system asymptotically stable, ascertain the solution to the problem using the linear matrix inequality method and estimate the gain for bounded delay Markov chains were used by the authors in [41], [42], [43] to simulate packet loss and networked delay caused by NCS. It is assumed that the system's uncertainty is moving either forward or backward. A set of stability conditions was estimated using the Lyapunov function to demonstrate the efficacy of the employed technique.

3. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Figure 1 depicts the suggested networked control system. Following the collection of plant samples, the data or measured signal is transferred from the sensor to the control.

The communication medium that the information/measured signal travels through could be susceptible to various kinds of uncertainty. For the plant to operate properly, the controller section computes the desired signal and forwards it to the actuator via a communication medium.

Fig. 1. NCS with disturbances (packet loss/delay)

A. Plant Description:

The linear time-invariant discrete system dynamics with disturbance are described as follows [40]:

$$x_{(k+1)} = Ax_{(k)} + Bu_{(k)} + \varphi_{(k)} \tag{1}$$

$$y_{(k)} = Cx_{(k)} + \omega_{(k)} \tag{2}$$

The A, B, C are matrices with the proper dimensions and the state-vector $x_{(k)}$, measurement signal $y_{(k)}$, control-vector $u_{(k)}$, and process Gaussian noise " $w_{(k)}$ " and measurement Gaussian white noise " $\varphi_{(k)}$ " with zero mean and covariance, Q and R , respectively, are the two types of noise. It is assumed to satisfy the controllability " (A, B) " and observability " (A, C) ".

B. Linear Quadratic Gaussian (LQG) control:

A quadratic objective function and a linear-state space approach form the foundation of the Linear Quadratic Gaussian (LQG) control. The LQG compensator's state-space representation is written as [40]:

$$x_{(k+1)} = (A - BK - LC + LDK)x_{(k)} + Ly_{(k)} \tag{3}$$

$$u_{(k)} = -Kx_{(k)} \tag{4}$$

where L is Kalman filter gain matrix and K is optimal-regulator gain matrices. The cost-function value is minimized by the control function that was designed as

$$J = \int_0^{\infty} [x^T Mx + u^T Nu] dt \tag{5}$$

where " Q " is the square-weighting matrix and " R " is the square-control-cost matrix which are symmetric and square.

C. Control Element

The actuator, which controls the plant to produce the intended response, receives the control action from the PID Controller. The PID control action is defined as

$$u(t) = K_p \left(e(t) + \frac{1}{T_i} \int_0^t e(t) dt + T_d \frac{de(t)}{dt} \right) \tag{6}$$

where K_p is proportional gain, $u(t)$ is the control signal, $e(t)$ is error signal, derivative time is T_d and T_i is integral time.

4. SIMULATION RESULT ANALYSIS

This section presents a numerical problem with simulation results to observe the suggested methodology. The methodology's efficacy is demonstrated by the addition of a different control action. The plant dynamics in this numerical problem are given by the following equations, which are explained below.

Transfer function of plant is:

$$G = \frac{3}{(3s + 1)} * \exp(-0.4 * s) \tag{7}$$

The compensator is defined by following expression

$$Comp = \frac{3s + 1}{(12s + 1)} \tag{8}$$

The MATLAB Simulink environment is used to run the simulation. The various simulated performance results are displayed in Figures 2 through 4. The Figure 2 simulation results demonstrate how the response signal continues to track the input signal even when a communication channel disturbance is introduced.

Fig. 2: Response signal without control action along with disturbance

Figure 3 present the response signal with control action along with disturbance in NCS. This demonstrates the efficacy of the suggested methodology.

The simulation diagram in Figure 4 displays comparative analysis of the response signal with and without control action along with disturbance in NCS. Different simulated diagram shows the effectiveness of proposed methodology.

Fig. 3: Response signal with control action along with disturbance

Fig. 4: Control signal generation without disturbance in NCS

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The networked control system's stability and transient performance are crucial because the introduction of an uncertain parameter degrades system performance and makes it unstable. Thus, the analysis of NCS system performance under uncertain conditions, such as disturbance, is the focus of this paper. The performance of NCS is demonstrated using control action and some appropriate stability conditions. The simulation's output, as seen in Figure 2, indicates that even when a communication channel disturbance is introduced, the response signal continues to track the input signal. Figure 3 present the response signal with control action along with disturbance in NCS. This demonstrates the efficacy of the suggested methodology.

The simulation diagram in Figure 4 displays comparative analysis of the response signal with and without control action along with disturbance in NCS. This demonstrates how successful the suggested methodology is.

Future research will focus on enhancing the nonlinear NCS's transient performance when faced with uncertainty and using optimal control scheme.

REFERENCES

1. X. Wang and M. D. Lemmon, "Event-triggering in distributed networked control systems," *IEEE Trans. Automat. Contr.*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 586–601, 2011.
2. R. Gupta and M. Y. Chow, "_Networked Control System Overview.pdf," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 57, no. 7, pp. 2527–2535, 2010.
3. Y. Wu, Y. Wu, and Y. Zhao, "An Enhanced Predictive Control Structure for Networked Control System with Random Time Delays and Packet Dropouts," *Proc. - 2016 3rd Int. Conf. Inf. Sci. Control Eng. ICISCE 2016*, pp. 834–838, 2016.
4. B. S. Solanki, "Stability and Performance Analysis of Networked Control System Experienced Variable Uncertain Dynamics," *Int. J. Mod. Dev. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 3, no. 9, pp. 6–10, 2024.
5. L. Lu and J. Lin, " H_∞ Output Tracking Control for Networked Control Systems with Long Time Delays," *Proc. 2018 Chinese Autom. Congr. CAC 2018*, pp. 892–897, 2018.
6. B. S. Solanki, "Controlled Output Feedback to Stabilize Networked Control System," *Int. J. Mod. Dev. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 3, no. 9, pp. 1–5, 2024.
7. B. Singh Solanki, R. Kumawat, and S. Srinivasan, "Optimal switching control design for industrial networked control system with uncertain exogenous dynamics," *Mater. Today Proc.*, vol. 79, no. xxxx, pp. 286–291, 2023.

8. X. Chen and S. Hu, "Event-based output tracking control for networked T-S fuzzy systems under non-periodic DoS jamming attacks," ANZCC 2018 - 2018 Aust. New Zeal. Control Conf., pp. 69–74, 2019.
9. Q. Zhang and F. Qu, "Stabilization of Networked Control Systems via Switching and Impulsive Controllers," Proc. 31st Chinese Control Decis. Conf. CCDC 2019, pp. 1852–1856, 2019.
10. P. Wang and G. Feng, "A study of optimal control strategy of networked control systems with stochastic delay and packet losses," CARE 2013 - 2013 IEEE Int. Conf. Control. Autom. Robot. Embed. Syst. Proc., pp. 1–5, 2013.
11. G. Bhatnagar, N. Gobi, H. Aqeel, and B. S. Solanki, "Sparrow-based Differential Evolutionary Search Algorithm for Mobility Aware Energy Efficient Clustering in MANET Network," Int. J. Intell. Syst. Appl. Eng., vol. 11, no. 8s, pp. 135–142, 2023.
12. X. Tang, M. Wu, M. Li, and B. Ding, "On Designing the Event-Triggered Multistep Model Predictive Control for Nonlinear System Over Networks With Packet Dropouts and Cyber Attacks," IEEE Trans. Cybern., pp. 1–13, 2021.
13. C. F. Caruntu and R. C. Rafaila, "Robust MPC for networked control systems with data-packet dropouts modeled as disturbances," 2017 21st Int. Conf. Syst. Theory, Control Comput. ICSTCC 2017, pp. 152–157, 2017.
14. H. C. Cho and M. S. Fadali, "Nonlinear network-induced time delay systems with stochastic learning," IEEE Trans. Control Syst. Technol., vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 843–851, 2011.
15. L. Hu, Z. Wang, and W. Naeem, "Security analysis of stochastic networked control systems under false data injection attacks," 2016 UKACC Int. Conf. Control. UKACC Control 2016, pp. 1–6, 2016.
16. R. Gupta, B. S. Solanki, M. Kumar, and R. Murugan, "Detecting Malware on the Android Phones Based on Golden Jackal Optimized Support Vector Machine," Int. J. Intell. Syst. Appl. Eng., vol. 11, no. 8s, pp. 01–07, 2023.
17. W. Lu, X. Yin, Y. Fu, and Z. Gao, "Observer-based event-triggered predictive control for networked control systems under dos attacks," Sensors (Switzerland), vol. 20, no. 23, pp. 1–21, 2020.
18. Q. Zhang, B. Liu, and W. Huang, "Stabilization of Nonlinear Networked Switched Control Systems with Delays and Packet Losses," Proc. 15th IEEE Conf. Ind. Electron. Appl. ICIEA 2020, pp. 332–338, 2020.
19. J. N. Singh and B. S. Solanki, "Utilization of Computational Intelligence in the Development of a Health Monitoring System for Induction Machines," 2022 Int. Conf. Futur. Technol. INCOFT 2022, pp. 1–6, 2022.
20. S. P. Singh and B. S. Solanki, "A Trading Model on Block chain Smart Contracts for the Shared Energy in Brazil," 4th Int. Conf. Emerg. Res. Electron. Comput. Sci. Technol. ICERECT 2022, pp. 1–5, 2022.
21. B. S. Solanki, "Design of an Optimal Reliable Controller for Industrial Networked Control System to Mitigate Network Imperfections," 2022.
22. M. Li et al., "Suppression of Disturbances in Networked Control Systems with Time-Varying Delay Based on Equivalent-Input-Disturbance Approach," IECON Proc. (Industrial Electron. Conf.), vol. 2019-Octob, pp. 6957–6960, 2019.
23. S. Solanki, B.S., Kumawat, R., Srinivasan, "Optimized Control Function with Estimation of System Parameters Against Attack for Networked Control System," in Intelligent Computing Techniques for Smart Energy Systems. Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering, 2022, vol. 862, pp. 515–528.
24. M. Zhu and S. Martinez, "On the performance analysis of resilient networked control systems under replay attacks," IEEE Trans. Automat. Contr., vol. 59, no. 3, pp. 804–808, 2014.
25. C. W. Ying and L. J. Yu, "Output Feedback Control of Networked Control Systems with Compensate for Packet Loss and Random Time Delays," Proc. - 2020 7th Int. Conf. Inf. Sci. Control Eng. ICISCE 2020, pp. 967–971, 2020.
26. B. S. Solanki, "Mitigating Effect of Uncertain Exogenous Dynamics by Parametric Performance Improvement with Optimal Control Design," Int. J. Eng. Trends Technol., vol. 70, no. 5, pp. 209–220, Jun. 2022.
27. Z. Gu, J. H. Park, D. Yue, Z. G. Wu, and X. Xie, "Event-Triggered Security Output Feedback Control for Networked Interconnected Systems Subject to Cyber-Attacks," IEEE Trans. Syst. Man, Cybern. Syst., vol. 51, no. 10, pp. 6197–6206, 2021.
28. B. S. Solanki, R. Kumawat, and S. Srinivasan, "Averting and Mitigating the Effects of Uncertainties with Optimal Control in Industrial Networked Control System," Proc. - 2021 IEEE Int. Symp. Smart Electron. Syst. iSES 2021, pp. 316–318, 2021.

29. Y. Su, J. Wu, C. Long, and S. Li, "Event-triggered Control for Networked Control Systems under Replay Attacks," Proc. 2018 Chinese Autom. Congr. CAC 2018, pp. 2636–2641, 2019.
30. H. Xu, S. Jagannathan, and F. L. Lewis, "Stochastic optimal design for unknown linear discrete-time system zero-sum games in input-output form under communication constraints," Asian J. Control, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 1263–1276, 2014.
31. B. S. Solanki, R. Kumawat, and S. Srinivasan, "An Impact of Different Uncertainties and Attacks on the Performance Metrics and Stability of Industrial Control System," in Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, 2021, vol. 204, pp. 557–574.
32. B. S. Solanki, R. Kumawat, and S. Srinivasan, "Synthesize the Effect of Intrusion and Imperfection on Networked-Connected Control System with Optimal Control Strategy," 2021 10th Int. Conf. Inf. Autom. Sustain. ICIAFS 2021, pp. 105–110, 2021.
33. T. Kumar, M. Sharma, and B. S. Solanki, "New Designs and Analysis of Multi-Core Photonic Crystal Fiber Using Ellipse with Different Radiuses and Angles," in International Conference on Artificial Intelligence: Advances and Applications 2019, 2020, pp. 151–159.
34. B. Singh and O. P. Sharma, "Analysis of BER in BPSK and GMSK Employing Different Coding," IFRSA's Int. J. Comput., vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 736–741, 2012.
35. B. S. Solanki, "Control System for Wind Power Plant," Int. J. Sci. Dev. Res., vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 473–476, 2019.
36. X. Tang, T. Li, S. Cong, and W. Qian, "Event-triggered adaptive control for networked control systems under two stochastic cyber-attacks," Proc. 31st Chinese Control Decis. Conf. CCDC 2019, pp. 170–175, 2019.
37. M. Li, J. She, Z. T. Liu, M. Wu, and Y. Ohyama, "Suppression of Packet Losses and Disturbances in Networked Control Systems Based on Equivalent-Input-Disturbance Approach," IEEE Trans. Cybern., vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 2051–2061, 2023.
38. Z. Wang, S. Fukushima, and T. Hachino, "Model Predictive Control Approach on Packet Dropout Prevention of Networked Control Systems," Proc. - 2018 5th Int. Conf. Inf. Sci. Control Eng. ICISCE 2018, pp. 839–843, 2019.
39. B. Singh, "Solar Power Generation by PV Technology," IRE Journals, vol. 1, no. 9, pp. 260–265, 2018.
40. B. S. Solanki, K. Renu, and S. Srinivasan, "Stability and Security Analysis with Identification of Attack on Industrial Networked Control System: An Overview," Internetworking Indones. J., vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 3–8, 2019.
41. B. Singh and O. P. Sharma, "Analysis of Coded and Uncoded Digital Modulation Techniques," Int. J. Electron. Commun. Technol., vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 46–48, 2013.
42. B. S. Solanki, "Review of Uncertain Dynamics in Networked Control System for Analysis of Stability," Int. J. Mod. Dev. Eng. Sci., vol. 3, no. 9, pp. 11–15, 2024.
43. J. Zhang, C. Peng, S. Masroor, H. Sun, and L. Chai, "Stability analysis of networked control systems with denial-of-service attacks," 2016 UKACC Int. Conf. Control. UKACC Control 2016, 2016.